

POSSIBILITIES OF USING INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN DISTANCE EDUCATION

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Abstract: this article provides information about the possibilities of using information technologies in distance education. Ways and possibilities of using various information and communication technologies in distance education are mentioned.

Key words: computer technologies, distance education, educational tools, professional knowledge, distance education, form of education, e-mail, electronic communication.

Today, great importance is attached to the development of computer technologies and the Internet. Accordingly, teaching of subjects related to vocational education along with informatics and new information technologies in educational institutions remains a demand of the time. In the distance education method, even if the teacher and the student are separated by a distance, constant communication is maintained. This will be done with the help of e-mail and Internet technologies, which will be a special way to monitor teaching. The introduction of modern information and communication technology tools into the educational process has led to the creation of a new form of education - distance education, in addition to traditional teaching methods.

In distance education, the student and the teacher are in constant communication with the help of specially created educational courses, control forms, electronic communication and other technologies of the Internet, while being separated from each other. Distance education based on the use of Internet technology provides access to the global information-educational network, performs an important series of new functions with the principle of integration and interaction.

Distance learning provides an opportunity for all those who want to learn to continuously improve their skills. In the process of such training, the student learns independent teaching and methodical materials in an interactive mode, passes control, performs control work under the direct supervision of the teacher and communicates with other students of the “virtual learning group” in the group.

For certain reasons, people who do not have the opportunity to study in full-time departments of educational institutions, for example, people who do not require health, who intend to change their specialty, or who are old, who intend to improve their qualifications. Distance education is a very convenient form of education.

Distance education uses various information and communication technologies, that is, each technology depends on the purpose and nature of the issue. For example, while traditional print-based teaching aids are based on introducing students to new material, interactive audio and video conferencing is based on timed interaction, e-mail, and feedback, that is, intended for sending and receiving messages.

The concept of “distance education” is special educational services based on the use of new information technologies that ensure the delivery of educational information to the recipient at a distance (via satellite, television, computer networks, etc.) recognized as a set.

Distance education is an educational complex based on means of exchanging educational information at a distance, where the teacher provides educational services to all levels of the population and foreign students with the help of a special information environment.

Distance education is a set of educational services aimed at special informational education for a wide segment of the population, implemented using means of educational information exchange (satellite, communication, television, radio, computer, etc.) is considered In distance education, the educational process uses traditional and innovative educational technologies, software and technical tools of education based on the use of computer equipment and telecommunications and other new information technologies. In distance education, the costs of study are

saved, there are no territorial restrictions, various modern technical means of study are used, there are opportunities to use the programs and teaching-methodical complexes of prestigious educational institutions.

In the method of distance education, the student and the teacher are in constant communication even if they are separated by distance. This is done with the help of e-mail and Internet technologies, which will be a special way to monitor teaching.

The goal of distance education is to increase the efficiency of independent work of students based on their programming knowledge, imagination and skills - to teach them to think scientifically, to increase their interest in academic subjects, to deepen their professional knowledge, and to increase their activity during theoretical and practical training. The share of distance education in such activity is large. It is known that the teaching model, technologies, and categories play a key role in distance education.

Distance education system is an education system organized on the basis of distance education conditions. Distance learning system, like all educational systems, has its structural purpose, content, methods, tools and organizational forms.

The use of distance learning technologies in the educational process has a strong impact on the positive changes in the content, forms and methods of education. Using distance education, it is possible to increase the general level of knowledge of the population and the quality of this knowledge. It will be possible to meet the voluntary requirements of all segments of the population. It is possible to disseminate knowledge to the general public in a timely manner. By creating a single educational environment, it is possible to embody all knowledge.

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